

www.bjisrd.com

Peculiarities of the Organization of the Educational Process in Foreign Language in a Technical University

Zukhra Allaberdievna Zulfiqorova,

Karshi engineering - economics institute, teacher at the Department of Foreign Languages

***Abstract:** The issue of teaching foreign languages in technical universities is covered in the article. The methods for teaching foreign languages that provide the biggest practical challenges for the way the educational system is set up are discussed. Analysis is done on several approaches to teaching foreign languages. The benefits and drawbacks of strategies and tactics that impede foreign language acquisition at this point in the learning process are taken into account. Modern techniques and theories are disclosed, which help students become motivated to learn a foreign language while also serving as a professional introduction to scientific and technical pursuits.*

***Key words:** foreign language, technical university, teaching methodology, teaching approach, communicative approach, learning process.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalised world, learning a foreign language is one of the most important jobs. Technological industry specialists use cutting edge technologies in their profession. Foreign language proficiency is definitely necessary for both their mastery and professional communication.

Technical specialties are among the most esteemed occupations in the modern world. A modern engineer is someone who speaks many foreign languages and has a high level of professional culture.

A future engineer must have an education that meets global standards, the primary requirement of which is proficiency in international languages, due to the demands of modern labour markets.

Discussions

It is important to define the term "organization," specifically "learning organization," before discussing how the learning process is organized in a foreign language. The way that learning is organized

involves a certain set of activities that students and teachers carry out in a specific order. It is a method of communication between the teacher and the student.

Several principles underpin how well the foreign language learning process is organized. These include:

- Considering the starting point of the student's knowledge. Students at technical universities typically have varying levels of proficiency in learning foreign languages.
- Giving students thorough and timely feedback.
- Development and preservation of a strong desire to learn. Students' capacity to acquire new information is hampered by their lack of enthusiasm and resistance to learning. Prior to beginning instruction, students must acquire new information and improve their speaking abilities in order to foster a high level of motivation.
- Using the newly learnt abilities.
- Give students the chance to apply the knowledge they have learnt in various training scenarios to real-world scenarios that they may encounter in their professional lives. This can involve having different conversations, studying technical books, viewing videos, etc.
- Considering the foregoing, it is safe to say that the structure of the foreign language education program at a technical university is determined by the department's teachers' consistent interactions with one another as well as the program's aims, objectives, and guiding principles.

To examine how foreign language teacher is organized in a technical university, one must first review the general teaching approach, parts of which are also employed in non-language universities. It suggests utilizing various strategies, techniques, and styles and kinds of foreign language instruction that are established by them.

The classical teaching methodology is the cornerstone of teaching foreign languages. The student advances from the lowest level of language learning to the highest using the classical teaching method. The teacher builds the linguistic attitude, teaches grammar, and stresses pronunciation. Reading, listening, and speaking are given careful consideration.

One of the drawbacks of this system is that it is taught by a teacher who speaks Uzbek or Russian. These educators can, nonetheless, obviously recognize, evaluate, and contrast languages and their constituent parts. The use of Russian or Uzbek speaking teachers to teach foreign languages is a drawback of this practice. Nonetheless, the teacher who speaks Russian or Uzbek can still assess, examine, and contrast the two languages and their constituent parts. It is easier for the teacher to anticipate problems and mistakes that the student may make, and to explain conventions and laws of language.

When teaching grammar and vocabulary, the teacher considers the sociocultural differences of the native speakers' country. In other words, the speech's content, but accuracy comes first. The primary feature of speech is its communicative nature.

The most often used method of teaching a foreign language is the communicative approach. Its main emphasis is on real-time, daily communication. This methodology's primary goal is to help students develop the appropriate psychological attitude in various scenarios.

In the era of advanced technology, intensive approach is becoming more and more common. This approach makes learning a foreign language simple since it uses common, stereotypical speech

constructs. It just involves memorization, and conversing openly with a native speaker is possible. We can see this from the numerous accelerated foreign language learning courses.

The test form of teaching a foreign language belongs to the important forms of work with foreign language learners. The disadvantage of this method is that the goal is not language learning itself, but only successful passing of tests.

There is a vast array of approaches used to teach foreign languages. The teacher possesses the authority to select the methodology and approach that aligns with the personal learning goals and objectives that they establish for themselves. These days, professional orientation, student self-education, and introduction to scientific and technological activities are all major goals of advances in the educational work of foreign language teachers at technical universities.

The most modern tools of foreign language teaching in technical universities are:

- ✓ situational language teaching using case technologies;
- ✓ trainings (e.g. business communication in production);
- ✓ project method, which helps students to develop their innovative teamwork abilities.

The project can be related to industrial practice or scientific and technical work that students are engaged in. The means that the teacher uses for learning a foreign language should take into account the latest achievements of technical science, correspond to the specialization of students and have some connection with their intended industrial career.

Conclusion

As a result, setting up a foreign language program at a technical university is an extremely intricate and responsible procedure. It is a drawn-out, dynamic process that is integrative, collaborative, and orientated in the professional realm. It involves educational and training activities as well as the use of both conventional and cutting-edge teaching styles, methods, and forms.

REFERENCES:

1. Зубков А.Д. Система обучения инбостранным языкам в техническом вузе / А.Д. Зубков // ИНФОУРОК – URL: <https://infourok.ru/sistema-obucheniya-inostrannim-yazikam-v-tehnicheskom-vuze-3478427.html>
2. Лихачева Ж.В. Организация обучения иностранным языкам в технических вузах / Ж.В. Лихачева // Омский научный вестник. – 2012. – № 5. – С. 225-228.
3. Anderson, N.J. (1999) Exploring Second Language Reading – Issues and Strategies Canada, Heinle & Heinle Bartlett, F.C. (1932) Remembering Cambridge, C.U.P. 4. Breen, M.P. (1985) Authenticity in the language classroom Applied Linguistics 6/1 pp60-70.
4. B.L.Kholmamatomvna Basic Principles of Teaching a Communicative Approach in a Foreign Language. <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1141> 262-257.2023
5. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatomvna. (2022). New trends of teaching English as foreign language. Open Access Repository, 8(03), 130–133. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/RK8HX>
6. Allaberdiyeva, Z. Z. (2022). Purpose of Teaching a Foreign Language in Non-language Higher Education Institutions. European Scholar Journal, 3(2), 79-80. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:xNb0X6qmPvYJ:scholar.google.com>

7. Allaberdievna, Zuhra Zulfiqorova & Sayfiyevna, Abdullayeva Shakhlo, Modern game technology in English lessons.2022. <https://philpapers.org/rec/ALLMGT>
8. Kholmamatovna, B. L. . . (2021). The Importance of Foreign Language Proficiency for Oil and Gas Industry Specialists. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 1(5), 167–170. <http://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/317>.